

**ACCOUNTING - AS PROVIDING A SYSTEM
FOR MANAGING ECONOMIC
INFORMATION IN AGRICULTURE**

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Abstract: The article examines how accounting provides the financial condition of agricultural enterprises. It is also indicated that accounting is a system based on the differentiation and dynamics of indicators allocated for assessing an enterprise, a set of interacting elements that ensure security against threats and risks, creating conditions for sustainable and safe strategic development.

Key words: accounting, financial security, budget, agriculture, assessment, element, system, risk, dynamics.

1. Introduction.

In today's rapidly evolving and constantly evolving age of rapid technical and technological change, the importance of timely, timely and accurate delivery of reliable information for managers, economists, marketers, accountants and other professionals is growing. The growing attention to this issue is reflected in the liberalization of the economy. It is important to deepen reforms, modernize the economy, ensure financial stability and security for all businesses in the context of expanding innovative activities. 70-80% of the total volume of economic information in agricultural enterprises falls on the share of accounting information. According to experts, until recently, the utilization rate of accounting information for management decisions was 10-12 percent. To date, this figure has been found to be even lower.

The current situation is the result of poor management of the management system with accounting information, as well as the low level of application of management accounting methods. In addition, it will be possible to identify the pros and cons that reflect the right management decisions at any time, and only if information is available that allows us to predict the expected outcomes.

Of course, all management functions are based not only on normative indicators, but also on accounting data that provide accurate information about the main activities. The accounting records reflect the actual existence and movement of economic assets, economic operations carried out in the process of turnover of fixed and working capital. Accounting provides the management system with information on the current quantitative and qualitative indicators, ie the property, liabilities and business processes of the business structure.

2. Analysis and results

In the current situation, information is needed to manage the activities of agricultural enterprises, which allows you to quickly identify differences in plans and norms. It is very difficult to verify the inputs and outputs obtained using the simple form of accounting, which operates on the principle of "cost-benefit", because they do not always have a deep economic meaning, so this information is rarely used in management. To do this, more attention should be paid to the proper organization of the budgeting process, which is an important element of management accounting.

Planning in agricultural enterprises is associated, first of all, with the identification of funding sources, the most optimal use of available financial resources and the rational use of self-financing sources.

The organization of sources of self-financing, that is, income-generating activities, does not violate the principle of unprofitability of agricultural enterprises. The fact that agricultural enterprises are not specifically directed to profit does not prohibit them from engaging in entrepreneurial activities, but it does mean that the profits received should be distributed in the interests of the founders or employees. To ensure effective operation, it is necessary to plan not only at the level of long-term strategy of agricultural enterprises, but also at the level of the set of programs they implement and individual day-to-day issues for each program. The logical continuation of the work on the formation of the financial plan is budgeting.

A budget is a financial forecast of the costs and sources of funding for the security of each program and the enterprise as a whole. The budget is calculated for a certain period of time. Although the budget is a forecast in its essence, it should be based on the most reliable data. Only in this case can it be classified as a prediction based on the highest probability.

Under the current circumstances, it is difficult for most agricultural enterprises to know exactly how much funding they can receive for the next year. Therefore, three types of budgets are required:

- Creating a minimum budget, which is based on the minimum costs required for the sustainable operation of enterprises. Funds to cover the minimum budget usually come from their own resources.

- Creating a guaranteed budget, which includes guaranteed expenditures with sufficient probability of financing. The same budget must be submitted by management for approval. It will be a key tool of financial management for the coming year.

- Creating an optimal budget, which includes all types of activities that have not yet been funded and is used in the preparation of proposals for fundraising.

Budget items are mainly divided into revenue and expenditure components.

Revenues indicate revenues that are expected to come from sources of financing, with a distinction between external and self-financing sources.

The expenditure part of the budget is divided into daily expenditures and capital investments. The traditional budget includes the following costs:

- salaries and social benefits;
- business trip expenses;
- material costs;
- information and communication costs;
- depreciation allowances;
- services of foreign farms;
- other expenses.

A budget is sometimes referred to as an estimate of revenues and expenditures. However, the concept of "budget" corresponds to the nature of future costs and revenues of planning activities in the context of uncertainty of the revenue side.

If the budget sections are depicted in tabular form, we see that it is similar to a traditional enterprise balance sheet. The same table itself is the balance of income and expenses.

The preparation of the annual budget of agricultural enterprises begins two months before the beginning of the fiscal year and must be approved before the beginning of the year.

The process of budgeting agricultural enterprises will be in three stages:

1. Analysis of the results of previous years;

2. Analysis of the current year's budget execution;
3. Planning for the next budget year.

The analysis of the results of previous years consists of identifying sections where the current performance of agricultural enterprises is lower or higher than expected. If last year's budget figures are close to reality, we will have incomplete data for the current year, completed last year. The analysis for the past few years will allow us to identify factors of a random nature that are not expected to be available in the budget next year and to adjust the forecast accordingly.

At this stage of budgeting, the company can have information about the planned sources of funding for the coming year, the planned programs and the costs associated with their implementation.

Planning, along with control, is one of the most important tasks of management and is the process of determining actions to be taken in the future.

Budget planning is the most detailed level of this process, the process of preparing a separate budget developed on the basis of programs approved by management for the structural units of the enterprise or by type of activity. Sometimes the term is interpreted as a complex system for choosing tactical planning goals at the enterprise level, developing a plan for the future activities of the enterprise (estimating costs and revenues) and monitoring the implementation of these plans, that is, in fact, an internal financial management system.

Uzbekistan currently has a regulatory framework for financial security of enterprises, which is regulated in 3 areas:

1. Regulatory framework of accounting regulation;
2. Tax administration;

3. Accounting policy.

The legal and regulatory framework of accounting is:

- Laws, Codes, Presidential Decrees, Government Resolutions.
- NASs, Regulations and Instructions developed by the Ministry of Finance, instructions, procedures and explanatory letters issued by the State Tax Committee.
- Instructions, guidelines, explanatory notes produced by other ministries and government agencies.
- internal normative documents representing the accounting policy of enterprises. The main regulatory framework is the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Accounting", adopted for the first time on August 30, 1996 and amended on 13.04.2016 (№404).

Also included are the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the "Regulations on the structure of costs of production and sale of goods (works, services) and the order of formation of financial results" adopted in 1999, legislation governing accounting and reporting and decisions of the Cabinet of Ministers.

The Law "On Accounting" is a key element of the accounting reform, defines unified accounting for all enterprises, institutions and organizations of various forms of ownership, establishes requirements for national accounting standards and provides the basic principles of the accounting system in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The purpose of this Law is to regulate the relations in the field of organization, maintenance and preparation of accounting.

The new version of the Law "On Accounting" contains 32 articles. According to the law, "Accounting is a regulated system of collection, recording and generalization of accounting information through a complete, continuous,

documentary accounting of all business operations, as well as the preparation of financial and other reports on its basis."

Accounting shall be carried out in a double-entry manner by reflecting the business transaction in at least two accounting accounts at the same time and in an interrelated manner, with monetary valuations.”

According to Article 3 of this law, continuity, reliability, comparability of indicators are defined as the basic principles of accounting. Accounting information is based on primary accounting documents, which are processed information about the objects of accounting, reflected in the accounting registers, financial statements, explanations and other documents related to the organization and maintenance of accounting. The new revised report also focused on the study of all knowledge according to accounting standards, or the minimum requirements related to the study of accounting for financial standards and the creation of financial statements. National Accounting Standards define the requirements for the organization of accounting and the creation of accounting and financial accounting. It is ensured that the accounting entities are supported in the prescribed manner in accordance with the rules that are allowed to the public by standards. Also, according to Article 7 of the Law "On Accounting", the accounting and reporting of enterprises must be organized by the head of the enterprise and the chief accountant. Methods of accounting include grouping and evaluation of evidence of economic activity, depreciation of assets, organization of document flow, inventory, methods of applying accounting records, maintenance of accounting registers and preparation of financial statements of the enterprise based on the information contained in them. The accounting policy of the enterprise is prepared by its accounting department and formalized by the head with the relevant organizational-command document.

Another normative document regulating accounting in Uzbekistan is the national accounting standards. National Accounting Standards set out specific requirements for the organization, maintenance and preparation of financial statements.

The guidelines and articles of the Law on Accounting have been developed in the National Accounting Standards (NAS) and 1-24 standards have been approved to date. Each standard has its own list of rules, determines the order of accounting in business entities and is an element of the system of normative regulation of accounting in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Among the most important documents of this level is the National Accounting Standard of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 21, approved by the Minister of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan on September 9, 2002 No. 103 and registered in the Ministry of Justice on October 23, 2002 No. 1181. - Accounting plan of economic activity and instructions for its application.

The next normative document is various orders, letters and instructions of a methodological nature provided by the Ministry of Finance, the Central Bank and other central government agencies of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Certain work is being done in the country to reform tax policy. In particular, the concept and strategy for improving tax policy have been developed and put into practice. The main directions of the strategy are to improve tax policy and reduce the level of clandestine turnover in the economy; development of service-oriented tax services; introduction of tax risk assessment system and improvement of tax accounting; further improvement of the state tax service; development of mechanisms to combat corruption in the state tax service. At the same time, the tax policy pursued in our country plays an important role in ensuring the financial stability and security of agricultural enterprises. In recent years, a number of regulations on tax policy have been adopted. In particular, a new version of the Tax

Code was adopted, which today serves as an important conductor of tax policy. Also, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On additional measures to improve tax administration" PP-4389, President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 18, 2017 "On measures to radically improve tax administration, increase tax collection and other mandatory payments" Decree No. 5116, Resolution of the President of the Republic Uzbekistan dated June 26, 2018 "On measures to radically improve the activities of the State Tax Service" and other documents continue to play an important role in the implementation of state tax policy and regulation of financial activities of enterprises. The purpose of these documents is to ensure the relationship between the enterprise and the tax authorities, in particular, to prevent problems in accounting and to ensure the overall integrity of tax policy and accounting policies.

This requires that the accounting policies developed by the enterprises be perfect. In recent years, the relevance of accounting policies has taken a significant place in foreign research. Indeed, the accounting policy clarifies the rules of accounting for each business entity. Finally, the internal regulatory documents relating to the accounting of an entity that only belong to a particular business entity are considered to be the regulatory framework aimed at ensuring its financial security. This is the accounting policy of the business entity, which is one of the legal bases of the organization of accounting. National Accounting Standard №. 1 of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Accounting Policy and Financial Reporting" is an element of the regulatory system of accounting.

The entity's accounting policy is developed by the chief accountant at the beginning of the reporting year and approved by the manager and must be applied throughout the reporting year without modification. In this standard, an accounting

policy is a set of methods adopted by the head of an entity to maintain accounting and prepare financial statements, financial statements are prepared in accordance with these methods and in accordance with their rules and principles.

Methods of grouping accounting and assessment of the facts of economic activity, methods of payment of assets, organization of document flow, property registration, methods of application of accounting reports, system of accounting registers, information processing and other relevant methods, methods of accounting enters. The chief accountant or other official performing accounting and financial management functions is the head of the accounting service. The head of the accounting service is directly subordinate to the head of the accounting entity.

In agricultural enterprises, too, the requirements of the head of the accounting service for the registration of business operations on the basis of documents and their submission to the accounting service are mandatory for all employees of the accounting entity.

1-National Accounting Standards are developed on the basis of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Accounting" and are an element of the system of accounting management in the Republic of Uzbekistan on a normative basis. This standard is used in conjunction with other national standards.

One of the legal bases for the organization of accounting is the accounting policy of agricultural enterprises. National Accounting Standard №. 1 of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Accounting Policy and Financial Reporting" is an element of the regulatory system of accounting.

With this in mind, in our opinion, the Accounting Policy is an internal normative document that reflects the specific normative methods chosen by the head of the agricultural enterprise for accounting and financial reporting and serves to

fully meet the information needs of users. According to National Accounting Standard No. 1, an agricultural enterprise must develop its own accounting policy for each fiscal year. Accounting policies include the grouping and valuation of business factors, the write-off of assets, the organization of document flow and inventory, the application of accounting records, the accounting system, the development of information and other relevant methods.

It is known that the accounting policy determines the order of preparation, purchase and valuation of tangible assets, the criteria for inclusion of items in property, plant and equipment or inventory and farm equipment, their obsolescence, the order of valuation and sale of finished products, the development of a chart of accounts. The accounting policy prepared for the next reporting year is a legal document after approval by the head of the enterprise.

Accounting policies represent the specific principles, conventions, procedures and practical approaches used by an agricultural enterprise to prepare and prepare financial statements. The accounting policy should be organized in such a way that the financial statements are prepared using all appropriate NASs. In the absence of special requirements, the financial statements:

- important for the needs of users;
- must be reliable in this regard:
- impartial presentation of all results of the entity's activities and financial condition;
- reflects not only the legal form, but also the economic nature of events and operations;
- impartiality and impartiality;
- be careful without compromising objectivity;

- all important aspects must be complete (complete), ie the subject must fully reflect all the facts of economic activity;
- comparable to the financial statements of other similar entities;
- should be clear.

In formulating the accounting policy of the entity in a particular area (issue), it is necessary to comply with the accounting laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the organization, maintenance and reporting of accounting.

The following issues are reflected in the accounting policy of the agricultural enterprise:

1. Organizational and technical issues:

- Document flow rules and schedule;
- internal reporting (composition, forms, periodicity, terms of creation and submission, users);
- internal control system (internal audit service, specialist, personally the head, the audit commission); - Regulations on accounting (or financial and accounting center) and division of responsibilities of employees of the accounting or financial accounting center (IMC);
- Inventory procedure.

2. Methodological issues:

- methods of controlling the deviation of the actual consumption of materials;
- the order of distribution of general production costs and other indirect costs;
- Procedure for writing off current expenses;
- identification of work in progress.

3. Tax issues:

- The order of organization of separate accounting (by type of activity, by goods sold, VAT at different rates, non-VAT, etc.);

- Organization of separate accounting of social facilities (in order to obtain the right to property tax benefits in the case of joint use of property in privileged and non-privileged industries).

The chosen accounting policy affects not only the efficiency of the implementation of accounting methods and techniques, but also the financial condition of the enterprise, the rational use of funds, the speed of management decisions.

At the same time, the purpose of accounting is to provide users with complete, reliable, timely financial and other information necessary to make sound business decisions.

3. Conclusion

With this in mind, the financial security of an agricultural enterprise is a system based on the differentiation and dynamics of indicators (indicators) allocated for the assessment of its status, a set of interacting elements that provide security from threats and risks, provide conditions for sustainable and secure strategic development. can be recognized.

From the above, we can see that today the economic reforms carried out in our country to ensure the security of financial resources of enterprises, their sustainable development are bearing fruit. At the same time, as a result of regulating the activities of agricultural enterprises, providing them with financial support and benefits, the strength of financial resources is stabilized and their security is fully ensured.

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